

Durability in a Heritage Context.

Big Stuff Conference, Ottawa, Canada, September 2013

Durability in a Heritage Context - Ottawa CA September 2013

Durability in a Heritage Context Adrian Stephan

Another flaw in the human character is that everybody wants to build and nobody wants to do maintenance. Kurt Vonnegut, Hocus-pocus

Farmer's comment:
"I am embarrassed
to show you the
mill."

Windmills on farms, Boonah District, Queensland, Australia. Images by A. Stephan

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Interest in the topic

- Based on partial outcome of doctoral research into the nature of maintenance work for plant and equipment
- Research inclusive of maintenance practices, tools and accounting for maintenance (historical & contemporary)
- **Maintenance work raison d'être is usefulness and value**
- Research lead to inquire into the maintenance work of heritage equipment
- A lot of high level descriptions but a lack of clarity in detail
- Started to ask questions and wound up here, in Canada!
- An extensive topic to cover – a starting point for further discussion

Home made wind generator c 1928, Templin Museum, Boonah, Queensland, Australia. Images by A. Stephan

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First People “Big Stuff”

- Natural and built “big stuff” of the First People of different lands
 - Tangible and intangible objects
- A different, but nevertheless significant, application of technology

Goebekli Tepe

Aboriginal Fish Traps

-
1. Goebekli Tepe in Southern Turkey. This site is about 11,000 years old and pre-dates Newgrange (about 5300 years ago), the Pyramid of Giza (about 4,700 years ago), and Stonehenge (about 4,600 years ago). Image source <http://ngm.nationalgeographic.com> (June 2011)
 2. Australian Aboriginal fish traps. Source: <http://au.totaltravel.yahoo.com/listing/1056108/australia/nsw/livingoutback/brewarrina-aboriginal-fis/>

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Mephisto (WWI A7V German tank)

- Only 20 were made.
- Mephisto is the sole remaining example
- Captured 22 July 1918 and transported to Queensland
- Current location is the Queensland Museum
- Extensive and intriguing battle and social history
- More or less intact. Probably saved due to being “out of sight”

A7V tank Mephisto, France, 1918. Image from Australian War Memorial. Image EO2876

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Further information can be found at:

<http://www.theworkshops.qm.qld.gov.au/Find+out+about/Histories+of+Queensland/Conflict/Mephisto>

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Mephisto

How long of a life should Mephisto be planned for? 300 years?

Images from Queensland Museum.

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Images sourced from:

www.theworkshops.qm.qld.gov.au/Find+out+about/Histories+of+Queensland/Conflict/Mephisto/Conservation

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Amiens Gun (German Rail Gun)

- Captured 8 August 1918 in France.
- The instruction was to destroy it but a soldier was an ex-train driver and was capable of moving the whole train
- Top image shows the gun as captured. The gun was complete and ready for firing plus 37 rounds of ammunition
- Bottom image shows the gun as it is now in situ at the Australian War Memorial
- Visit www.awm.gov.au for more information

Images from Australian War Memorial and Creative Commons

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Images sourced from:

<http://www.awm.gov.au/collection/P01887.001>

The 'Amiens Gun' captured by Australian soldiers in 1918 on display at the Australian War Memorial in 2009. <http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/User:Nick-D>

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About the Topic

- Saving Big Stuff in Tight Economic Times
- The scope is the maintenance of the objects and not the facility
- Tight Economic times:
 - Probably challenging most of the time
 - Is it any different to other industries?
- Economics:
 - “The study of how society chooses to allocate its scarce resources to the production of goods and services in order to satisfy unlimited wants”
 - Scope: capital, labour and land
 - Economic capital is the physical plant, machinery and equipment used to produce goods and services. It is not money
- The “saving problem” is to make decisions that are the best allocation of scarce resources
- Scarce resources can change status over time
- Saving is determined by the choices and commitments that individuals or society are willing to make over time about the significance of plant and equipment for the benefit of future generations

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Questions and Decisions (Q&D)

- What plant and equipment needs to be saved?
- Why does it need to be saved – its “value proposition”?
- How can it be saved – acquisition, sustainment?
- How will it be used to produce goods and services?
- What are those goods and services?
- Will these goods and services change over time?
- How will they change?
- Will there be a change of custody of the plant and equipment?
- How many lives does the plant and equipment actually have? Total Life Profile
- How must the plant and equipment be sustained?
- How is performance measured?
- How durable does the object have to be?

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Statistics Australian (AU) Museums

- In June 2008 there were 1,019 museums at 1,276 locations. These included: 768 social history collections, 425 historic properties and 83 others
- In June 2008 there were 49.6 million objects
- Source: www.abs.gov.au 4172.0 Arts & Culture in Australia, Museum Fact Sheet

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Maintenance

- Comparing maintenance with conservation, restoration, etc terminology
- The action of keeping something in working order, in repair, etc.; the keeping up of a building, institution, body of troops, etc., by providing means for equipment, etc.; the state or fact of being so kept up; means or provision for upkeep. (Shorter Oxford English Dictionary - SOED)
- The upkeep of property or equipment . (Merriam-Webster Dictionary)

Car on the back of a truck crossing Local the flooded Pine Creek Bridge, Numbinah Valley, Queensland, Australia, circa 1936.
Photographer unknown. Image from Gold Coast Studies Library.

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Image sourced from Gold Coast Local Studies Library:

Spen and Nancy Yaun's 1936 Plymouth car on the back of the Yaun Brother's International Truck crossing the flooded Pine Creek Bridge, Numbinah Valley, Queensland, circa. Photographer unknown. The family were on their way to a funeral in Southport. LS-LSP-CD035-IMG0044

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Same term - different outcome

- Spalling:
 - Where small pieces of stone flake off or split into chips; usually caused by frost damage. (Australian International Cultural Council - AICC)
 - Mechanical spalling occurs at high stress contact points. e.g. bearings
 - Good examples of bearing spalling can be found on the web – see note
- It is usually a critical failure mode – i.e. the machine literally grinds to a halt
- How many bearings do you rely on in a given day? e.g. Aircraft turbine bearings, 100+ in car
- Autonomic logistics & health and usage management systems (HUMS) to manage bearing condition, etc
- What is the impact of mechanical spalling in a museum mechanical object?

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Classic Bearing Damage Modes. Ryan D. Evans, Ph.D. Manager, Bearing Fundamentals & Tribology

The Timken Company, Wind Turbine Tribology Seminar, NREL Argonne DoE, Broomfield, CO, USA, November 2011

http://www.nrel.gov/wind/pdfs/day2_sessioniii_4_timken_evans.pdf

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Meaning of Durability

- Capable of lasting or continuing in existence; persistent, lasting; not transitory, permanent (from SOED)
- IEC 60050 International Electrotechnical Vocabulary 191-02-02
- **durability** the ability of an item to perform a required function under given conditions of use and maintenance, until a **limiting state** is reached
- *Note – A **limiting state** of an item may be characterized by the end of the useful life, unsuitability for any economic or technological reasons or other relevant factors*

Figure 191-2 - Performance concepts

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Durability Factors

- Ability:
 - The quality or state of being able to meet expectations – its capability
- Required function:
 - What the plant and equipment is expected to do
 - Original or degraded functions
 - Authenticity
- Given conditions of use:
 - Dynamic – own power or driven – under load or no-load
 - Static
 - Storage
- Limiting state is pivotal issue. This state sets the baseline for all maintenance work.

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Durability Limiting State Factors

- Political plans and commitment
- Compliance
- Property owner's interests – is it only rubbish?
- Economic conditions
- Accounting practices – e.g. depreciation
- Technological state
- Social – choices, values, etc
- Inherent characteristics – physical degradation of materials - oil
- Induced characteristics – vibration, electromagnetic – solar flares, lightening, etc
- Use expectation – can a use profile be determined with a realistic expectation
- Skill to operate and maintain – qualifications sustainment
- Know-how loss – loss of tacit knowledge
- Parts and documentation – key aspects of maintenance – particularly with age
- Ability to forecast the future
- Education and training

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Effective Life

- Effective Life
 - How long it can be used to produce income, taking into account:
 - Wear and tear under expected conditions of use
 - Level of maintenance (Australian Tax Office)
- Production asset life:
 - Meets the needs of why the asset was designed in the first place
 - E.g. water wheel to power factory
- Social asset life:
 - No longer productive but has social value for learning or historical purposes

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Durability Through Life Plan

A Through Life Plan is probably the most critical document for durability.

It will vary from project to project, but the general scope of a plan is:

- Define the durability objectives of the study or studies
- Define the scope of the analysis
- Specify key durability driving parameters
- State any conditions, assumptions, constraints, or requirements
- Identify the possible alternative courses of action evaluated
- Estimate resources required to achieve the durability goal
- Develop cost breakdown structure (CBS) & work breakdown structure (WBS)
- Heritage needs to be included as part of the life cycle planning processes from the beginning

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Product Life Cycle Phases

For each item you select, make sure you know its position in the product life cycle.

Phases:

- Introduction
- Growth
- Maturity
- Decline

Make sure you know how long a product will be supported.

These are the LCM Challenges

Heritage should be part of this analysis.

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Equipment Life Cycle Phases

- Market, Need identification
- **Concept**
- **Demonstration & Validation**
- **Full Scale Development**
- **Production**
- Operations & Support
- **Disposal or Phase-out**
 - Includes reuse
 - Transition to new use
 - Heritage

} Translation Phase
Concept to Product

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End of Life Transition

- AS4536 Disposal cost elements
- This is where the transition needs to be costed
- Keep in mind that some of these costs are estimated at project beginning
- This is the point of transition to a new through life plan
- Include cost of transition to heritage as part of the disposal costs

Non-Recurring Costs:

- Equipment Shutdown
- Equipment Disassembly & Removal
- **Transition to new life (proposed)**
- Support Closeout
- Hazardous Materials
- Surplus Equipment
- Refurbishment/Deactivation
- Product's Residual Value

Recurring Costs:

- Waste Fuels, Lubricants, Cleaning Materials
- Broken, Discarded Parts or Equipment
- Packaging Material

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New Life Transition Costs

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Heritage Through Life Issues

- Planned for from the earliest analysis of the equipment
- There is enough evidence to show that this need is known
- Financial issues such as cost
- Laws and regulations revision needed
- Compliance
- Technical issues such as availability of parts, documents, on going know how, and very importantly any intellectual property issues.
 - Integrated collection - Relies on good inventory management system to link it all together
 - *bundling of equipment, spares, tools and all documentation – better value*
- Setting durability use and limiting states

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Life Estimation

- O'Connor has good material on life data analysis
- General Case

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O'Connor, P. D. T. and A. Kleyner (2012). Practical reliability engineering. Chichester, Wiley.

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Weibull Distribution

Unreliability

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Non-Age Related Failure

- Contemporary experience is showing that failure modes are not conforming to expectations
- Failures are showing to be constant irrespective of age:
 - Failures due to dynamic stress loads
 - Failures due to increased complexity of equipment
- It is all about the relationship between the distributions of strength and load – it's that simple!

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The top diagram shows that the distribution of load and strength do not overlap and in this case any failure would be purely random.

The next diagram shows that the strength has remained the same, but the load has increased. In this case there is overlap and there is probability of failure.

The bottom diagram shows that the load is the same, but the strength has decreased. In this case there is overlap and there is probability of failure.

If the distributions can be made tighter, then there is no need to have such a strong design for the load and thus reduce costs.

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Preservation

- Expected to be a major issue:
 - Defence practices might be relevant in some cases
 - Similar type of problem. How do we keep stuff in operational ready or another useful state
- ADF Australian Defence Force Packaging Standard Part 3 – Packaging Practices and Materials – 258 pages
- ABCA (American British Canadian Australia) - procedural principles and comparison of preservation methods
- View the Australian Defence Force standards online for more information

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Further information:

http://www.defence.gov.au/dmo/lcd/standards/def_aust_1000.cfm

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Corn Husker & 1922 Austin Tractor

Agricultural machinery, Templin Museum, Boonah, Queensland, Australia. Images by A. Stephan

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Storage Condition

Storage, Queensland, Australia. Images by A. Stephan

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Asset Deterioration

- There is a point (P) at which the failure is identified
- This failure growth continues until the functional failure (F) occurs
- Once the potential failure is detected at P, a maintenance task can be taken to avoid functional failure at F – assuming there is enough time available.
- On-Condition tasks must be carried out at intervals less than the P-F interval
- Sporadic & chronic failures
 - Sporadic – procedure solution
 - Chronic – innovative solutions

Scheduled on-condition tasks are feasible if:

- It is possible to define a clear potential failure condition
- The net P-F interval is the period long enough to take effective maintenance action

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Failure Mode Effects Criticality Analysis (FMECA)

- Its objective is very simple: catalogue failures and analyse them in a robust and systematic way.
- By analysing them it is possible to improve to remove or mitigate failure modes and then develop maintenance strategies to address failures during operations. i.e. make the equipment more durable
- Any maintenance and maintenance support strategy must be based on a FMECA – without a failure there is no need for maintenance or resources.
- The criticality aspect enables the ordering the failure modes based on the severity classification of the consequences.
- No reason why this process cannot be adapted to any object.
- FMECA Standards: US MIL-STD-1629A, SAE J1739, IEC 60812, ISO/TS 16949 (auto)

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Maintenance Policy

- The maintenance policy determines whether or not a specific item is to be maintained or not maintained.
- This decision is usually based on life cycle cost and technological capability.
- It may not be cost effective to maintain items due to issues such as:
 - Cost of spares
 - Skill retention
 - Technology
 - Transportation
 - Maintenance facilities
- The policy analyses and decisions are recorded in the maintenance plan.

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Maintenance Task Register

- FMECA drives the need for a maintenance task.
- Unless there is a failure event (FMECA), there is no need for a maintenance event.
- In process terms, converting the maintenance task analysis into actual tasks, is a significant set of events and processes.
- It is the basis for the maintenance program.
- The structure and content will vary on the work involved.
- It should not involve too many fields of data – only those actually needed for decision making.

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Maintenance Task Register Outline

- Identification code
- Name
- Part number
- Model number
- Manufacturer
- Serial Number
- Alternate assets
- Cost information
- Maintenance frequency
- Maintenance tolerance
- Maintenance venue
- Maintenance skills
- Documentation
- Time run
- Fault history
- Repair history

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Asset Registers

- There are two registers:
 - Physical. What an asset looks like
 - Functional. What an asset does
- Both registers are important for:
 - Asset condition & performance measurement.
 - Reliability, maintainability and availability data roll-up
 - Setting maintenance programs.
 - What has to be maintained
 - Functional expectation of maintenance

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Data Codification

- Codification is the linchpin for the structure of the maintenance system
- Used to uniquely identify each location in the asset structure:
 - Which parts can fit that location (configuration)
 - Maintenance plan for parts in that location
 - Performance of parts in that location
- Same part number may be used in several different locations but have different performances due to environment, accessibility, etc...
 - Vibration, operating temperature, temperature cycles, humidity, contamination, etc

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Change (Configuration) Management

- Change can happen to plant, processes and people:
 - Plant – different part number, supplier, design, product mix, use
 - Processes – different torque wrench setting, application of paint, cutting grass, etc
 - People – Change of senses (smell, hearing, sight, touch, allergy, writing, etc)
- All of these changes must be addressed in dealing with an asset. Don't assume it will be constant.
- ISO 10007 Quality management systems – Guidelines for configuration management
 - This standard is probably more important than ISO 9000
 - This standard will manage authenticity and integrity of objects
 - Manage conjectural interpretations

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Maintenance Task Plan

- Plans can be structured to reflect categories based on:
 - Statutory and safety
 - Environmental
 - Production
- Typical maintenance tasks include:
 - Lubrication
 - Inspection
 - Overhaul, restoration or refurbishment tasks
 - Scheduled replacement tasks
 - Servicing tasks

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Maintenance Resource Plan

- Maintenance cannot be undertaken without resources, such as:
 - Budget
 - Skills
 - Training (three levels: community, trade & undergraduate)
 - Documentation
 - Spares
 - Tools
 - Facilities
 - Management
 - Accommodation & travel

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Accounting Standards

- **UN SNA08** – System of National Accounts
- **IFRS** – International Financial Reporting Standards
- **AASB** – Australian Accounting Standards Board
 - AASB 116 Property, Plant and Equipment

Australian Government
Australian Accounting Standards Board

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Further information:

www.

<http://unstats.un.org/unsd/nationalaccount/sna2008.asp>

www.ifrs.org

www.aasb.gov.au

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Future Considerations

- An object could have many sequential lives, and all different
- Total life planning for durability should take place during first acquisition
- Accounting should be relevant for museum objects.
 - Look out for “accounting creep”
- Education for heritage maintenance – community, trade and undergraduate
- Use of virtual attendance technology – virtual books.
- Change standards such as accounting and through life cost to include heritage considerations.
- Change relationship with property owners to look after the “unstructured museum objects” in return for alternatives on rates, taxation and property use.

WWI field gun believed to be at Southport, Queensland, circa 1920. Photographer unknown. Image from Gold Coast Local Studies Library

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Image sourced from Gold Coast Local Studies Library:

Two unidentified women and man on the World War 1 field gun believed to be at Anzac Park, Southport, Queensland, circa 1920. Photographer unknown. LS-LSP-CD129-IMG0018

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Wrap-up

- Durability is an appropriate integrated framework to study Big Stuff sustainment.
- Industrial maintenance practices are applicable to museum Big Stuff objects.
- Outcome is good analysis to minimize risk to durability.
- Plight of heritage items need more visibility & understanding.
- Probably more of a political commitment problem than a technical one

Crane accident while removing the Southport Memorial Clock, Nerang and Scarborough Streets, Southport, Queensland, Australia, 1970. Bob Avery, photographer. Image from Gold Coast Local Studies Library.

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Image sourced from Gold Coast Local Studies Library:

Crane accident while removing the Southport Memorial Clock, Nerang and Scarborough Streets, Southport, Queensland, 1970. Bob Avery, photographer. LS-LSP-CD578-IMG0003

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Relevant Reading

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- US MIL-STD-1629A Failure Mode Effects Criticality Analysis

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Associations that might be of Interest

- Society for Industrial Archeology – www.siahq.org
- The International Molinology Society – www.molinology.org
- Engineering Heritage Australia - <http://www.engineersaustralia.org.au/engineering-heritage-australia>
- <http://www.aiccm.org.au>
- <http://www.collectionsaustralia.net>
- <http://www.museumsaustralia.org.au> (which includes link to groups like this <http://manexus.ning.com> and a range of special interest networks)
- <http://www.alia.org.au>
- <http://www.archivists.org.au>
- <http://www.aiatsis.gov.au>
- <http://www.environment.gov.au/heritage/ahc/index.html>
- <http://www.conservationvolunteers.com.au>
- <http://australia.icomos.org>

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Australian Collections – a small selection

Australian War Memorial <http://www.awm.gov.au>
National Trust of Australia <http://www.nationaltrust.org.au>
Australian Museum <http://australianmuseum.net.au>
Queensland Museum <http://www.qm.qld.gov.au>
The Workshops Rail Museum <http://www.theworkshops.qm.qld.gov.au>
Museum of Victoria <http://museumvictoria.com.au>
The Powerhouse Museum <http://www.powerhousemuseum.com>
Tasmanian Museum and Art Gallery <http://www.tmag.tas.gov.au>
South Australian Museum <http://www.samuseum.sa.gov.au>
Western Australian Museum <http://museum.wa.gov.au>
Museums and Art Galleries of the Northern Territory <http://artsandmuseums.nt.gov.au/museums>
National Museum of Australia <http://www.nma.gov.au>
National Film and Sound Archives <http://www.nfsa.gov.au>
National Library of Australia <http://www.nla.gov.au>
National Archives of Australia <http://www.naa.gov.au>
Templin Historical Village <http://www.boonahtourism.org.au/factsheet.php?id=67>
Gold Coast Local Studies Library <http://www.goldcoast.qld.gov.au/library>

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Victorian Government Australia website “Industrial Heritage Adaptive Reuse Case Studies”

http://www.dpcd.vic.gov.au/heritage/projects-and-programs/industrial-heritage-case-studies?utm_source=buffer&utm_campaign=Buffer&utm_content=bufferf45dc&utm_medium=twitter

Durability in a Heritage Context.

Big Stuff Conference, Ottawa, Canada, September 2013

Durability in a Heritage Context - Ottawa CA September 2013

Thank you!

Bi-plane being started on the beach, Gold Coast, Australia, circa 1920s. Photographer unknown. Image from Gold Coast Local Studies Library

Need more information or want to continue the conversation?

Contact details next slide

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Image sourced from Gold Coast Local Studies Library:

Bi-plane on the beach being started, Gold Coast, circa 1920s. Photographer unknown. LS-LSP-CD080-IMG0100

Durability in a Heritage Context.

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